

Thickened Flame LES methodology for turbulent propagating flames in non-homogeneous mixtures: application to a constant volume chamber.

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Abstract

A Large Eddy Simulation methodology is presented in the framework of the Thickened Flame model, to predict the dynamics of turbulent propagating flames in non-homogeneous mixtures at variable pressure and temperature. At first, an analytical model is introduced to evaluate dilution by burnt gases and correct the chemical scheme. This method is then coupled with a new combustion model (the Stretched-Thickened Flame model or S-TF) allowing to capture stretch effects on thickened flame fronts. The S-TF model is also extended to accommodate multiple gas conditions. This numerical approach is applied to simulate multiple cycles of the pistonless constant volume combustion (CVC) chamber CV2, operating at the Pprime laboratory in Poitiers, France. The experimental ignition sequence and flame propagation is taken as reference. Results demonstrate the capability of this model to predict flame evolution in the CVC chamber. Comparisons with the classical Thickened Flame model underscore the effectiveness of the S-TF model, also for turbulent flames.

Keywords: Unsteady propagating flames; Stretched-Thickened Flame model; Dilution; Residual Burnt Gases

1. Introduction

Combustion in constant volume chambers (CVC) is an effective solution to increase the efficiency of gas turbines [1, 2], because, like Rotating Detonation engines, they offer higher theoretical efficiency compared to constant-pressure combustion systems [3]. Their simulation, however, raises multiple challenges, very similar to those found in classical piston engines [4, 5].

Large Eddy Simulation (LES) has taken an increasingly significant role in this field, but still requires advanced physical models to ensure predictive computations. Ignition, high pressure, dilution, flame-turbulence interaction, stretch effects, are just part of numerous challenges that have to be accomplished in different combustion processes and especially in CVC flows. In particular, increasingly sophisticated and comprehensive combustion models are required. The Thickened Flame (TF) model [6, 7] has been extensively used to capture combustion processes and different numerical approaches have been proposed to exploit its advantages in multiple combustion systems. Lacaze [8] focused on spark ignition, introducing the Energy Deposition model to ignite a flame before thickening it and capture the first instants of kernel-flow interaction [1]. The TF model has been extended for non-homogeneous mixtures at variable pressure and temperature [9, 10] and ignition sequences have been analysed in more complex scenarios. In the context of afterburners, Mocquard et al. [11, 12] stressed the importance of considering dilution in the TF model application and developed a modeling strategy to evaluate dilutants concentrations in perfectly premixed flames. Volpiani et al. [13] highlighted the necessity to account for stretch effects in the resolution of unsteady propagating turbulent flames. Once ignited, these flames are advected by the surrounding flow and, if the reaction zone is thickened, the flame response may be affected by the resolved stretch acting on it [14-17]. The Stretched-Thickened Flame (S-TF) model [15] accomplishes this purpose and it has been theoretically developed and tested in simple perfectly premixed laminar flames. Additional effort is still needed to reach a numerical framework able to embrace all these phenomena and approach complex scenarios, where non-homogeneous mixtures, non-constant fresh gas conditions, dilution with combustion products and highly stretched flames increase the complexity of the physics involved.

In this work, a novel LES methodology is proposed in order to enhance the Thickened Flame model predictions of time-dependent turbulent propagating flames. The subsonic constant volume combustion chamber CV2, experimentally investigated by Michalski et al. [2] and numerically by Bonneau et al. [18] with tabulated chemistry method, is used as test case. The unsteady nature of this chamber makes this set-up a valuable choice to evaluate the maturity of the LES methodology. Moreover, another pecu-

Fig. 1: a) CV2 combustion chamber details. b) Averaged experimental pressure signal over multiple cycles [2].

liarity of CVC flows is the presence of residual burnt gases affecting the fresh charge from one cycle to another. The dilution model proposed in [11, 12] is reformulated here and applied to a CVC engine. The S-TF model theory [15] is extended for non-constant fresh gas conditions. These two advanced LES models are coupled and their implications in the numerical simulations are examined.

First, the experimental set-up of the CV2 chamber is briefly recalled (Sect. 2). In Sect. 3 the numerical framework is described followed by the dilution model. Finally the S-TF model is extended to different flame conditions (Sect. 4.3) and applied to the test case (Sect. 5).

2. Experimental Setup

The CV2 test rig operated at Pprime laboratory (Poitiers, France) investigates cyclic constant volume combustion processes for air-breathing gas turbines. Figure 1a illustrates the main features of the chamber set-up with the main diagnostics. The experimental reference sequence [2] has twelve consecutive cycles with separate injection of air and propane (C_3H_8/Air) at stoichiometric ratio. Each cycle is divided into four phases (Fig. 1b): 1. admission: air and fuel are injected inside the chamber; 2. combustion at constant volume; 3. isochoric cooling; 4. exhaust: burnt products are released outside the combustor. During each cycle, spark ignited turbulent flame propagates in a stratified mixture, affected by different dilutants concentration, while the gas pressure increases. Turbulent flow corrugates and stretches flame surface, contributing significantly to its temporal dynamics.

3. Numerical method

A series of consecutive cycles at 8 Hz is simulated using the compressible solver AVBP [19] (<https://www.cerfacs.fr/avbp7x/>). The Navier-Stokes equations convective terms for reacting flows are solved with the TTGC scheme (3rd order accurate in space and time) [6] and the diffusive terms are discretized applying the Galerkin finite element method to viscous fluxes [20]. The integration in time is explicit, limited by the acoustic CFL number (0.7). The

Fig. 2: Sketched representation of the CV2 flammable mixture before combustion. Mass fractions of CO_2 and H_2O come from the previous combustion phases.

subgrid Reynolds stresses are modeled by the WALE turbulent closure [21]. Inlet and outlet boundary conditions are treated as proposed in [10], assuming that intake and exhaust valves behave as convergent-divergent nozzles. Walls are treated as no-slip. Thermal losses are applied to walls imposing heat resistances compliant with the chamber material. A two-step chemistry with constant non-unity Lewis number ($Le^0 = 1.4$ for all the species as suggested in [22]), presented in [10] and extended for wide ranges of pressure, temperature and equivalence ratio, is used:

Further information is found in Supplementary material. In Sect. 4.1 this mechanism is extended for diluted flames. Flame kernel is ignited using the Energy Deposition (ED) model [8, 10] and the propagating flame is resolved on the LES grid with the Stretched-Thickened Flame (S-TF) model [15], extended here for non-homogeneous and variable fresh gas conditions (Sect. 4.3). The standard Charlette turbulence combustion model [23] ($\beta = 0.5$) is used to deal with subgrid turbulent combustion. Five points are required in the flame front [10]. In the LES, the conservative Navier-Stokes variables and the six species composing the scheme are transported.

A uniform mesh is used with a $\Delta x = 0.4$ mm except near the spark ignition region where it is refined ($\Delta x = 0.1$ mm) to have a sufficient number of points in the energy deposition zone. Approximately 50 million cells are used to discretise the whole domain.

4. LES models for dilution and stretch

4.1. Modeling for dilution

At the beginning of the sequence, fuel and oxidizer are separately injected in pure air generating a non-homogeneous flammable gas. Starting from second cycle, flame propagates within a fuel-air mixture, diluted by the residual products coming from former cycles. Figure 2 sketches the CVC mixing problem during the generic cycle.

As emphasized in [11, 12], the dilution of the fresh mixture by Residual Burnt Gas (RBG) has to be accounted for in LES simulations. Even though two-step mechanisms are able to capture fuel/air combustion, they fail when it comes to diluted flames, asking for specific corrections. Moreover, flame/turbulence models require local fresh gas conditions to derive laminar flame parameters. For example, the flame thickness is required to determine the thickening factor [7] and the laminar flame speed is needed by the turbulent combustion model [23]. Therefore, dilution levels and their impact on combustion must be characterized.

The dilution model proposed by Mocquard et al. [11] is reformulated for the CV2 test case, where the combustion process occurs in a mixture composed by $\text{C}_3\text{H}_8/\text{O}_2/\text{CO}_2/\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{N}_2$. The approach relies on a complete combustion assumption. The implications of this hypothesis are discussed in Sect. 5.

For each cycle, the diluted flammable mixture is characterized by an effective equivalence ratio ϕ_r :

$$\phi_r = s \frac{Y_{\text{C}_3\text{H}_8}}{Y_{\text{O}_2}} \quad (3)$$

where $Y_{\text{C}_3\text{H}_8}$ and Y_{O_2} are the mass fractions of fuel and oxidizer available in the chamber (Fig. 2), while s is the mass stoichiometric ratio (equal to 3.63 for propane/air mixtures). Prior to each spark-ignition, the local concentrations of $Y_{\text{C}_3\text{H}_8}$ and Y_{O_2} encompass the presence of fuel and oxidizer introduced during each intake phase, along with any remaining unreacted species from preceding combustion events.

The complete composition of the reacting gas is also identified by the equivalence ratio ϕ_{tot} , accounting locally for all masses injected inside the system:

$$\phi_{tot} = s \frac{Y_{\text{C}_3\text{H}_8} + Y_{\text{C}_3\text{H}_8}^*}{Y_{\text{O}_2} + Y_{\text{O}_2}^*} \quad (4)$$

where $Y_{\text{C}_3\text{H}_8}^*$ and $Y_{\text{O}_2}^*$ correspond to the mass fractions of the amount of fuel and oxidizer introduced in the chamber and burnt in the previous cycles. $Y_{\text{C}_3\text{H}_8}^*$ and $Y_{\text{O}_2}^*$ are responsible for the consumption of carbon and hydrogen producing CO_2 and H_2O , (when CO is neglected), diluting the flammable mixture (see Fig. 2). Moreover, Mocquard et al. [11, 12] demonstrated that ϕ_{tot} and ϕ_r are linked by a third quantity ϕ_{bg} :

$$\phi_{bg} = s \frac{Y_{\text{C}_3\text{H}_8}^*}{Y_{\text{O}_2} + Y_{\text{O}_2}^*}, \quad (5)$$

tracking the mass fraction of fuel burnt in the previous cycles. ϕ_{tot} , ϕ_r and ϕ_{bg} are linked by [11] (see Supplementary material):

$$\phi_r = \frac{\phi_{tot} - \phi_{bg}}{(1 - \phi_{bg})}, \quad (6)$$

which is used in Sect. 4.4 to describe the practical implementation of the model in the LES. Consequently, only two of these three parameters (e.g. ϕ_r and ϕ_{bg})

Fig. 3: Laminar flame speed s_L^0 computed with the corrected two-step chemistry (2-step), CRECK mechanism [24], San Diego mechanism [25]. $P = 3 \text{ bar}$, $T = 350 \text{ K}$.

1 are necessary to define the composition of the mix-
2 ture.

3 4.2. Global chemistry correction

4 As shown in [11], the accuracy of global
5 chemistries in the prediction of diluted flames prop-
6 erties is enhanced by adjusting the forward reactions
7 rates ($k_{f,j}$) of the two-step mechanism (Eqs. (1)-(2))
8 using functions of ϕ_{bg} and ϕ_r :

$$k_{f,i} \mapsto k_{f,i} h_i(\phi_r, \phi_{bg}), \quad i = 1, 2. \quad (7)$$

9 The pre-exponential correction functions $h_i(\phi_r, \phi_{bg})$
10 are adjusted to match the flame speed and adiabatic
11 temperature of the detailed mechanism.

12 Figure 3 shows the laminar flame speed s_L^0 com-
13 puted with the two-step chemistry, for $\phi_{bg} =$
14 0.0/0.2/0.3 and validated against the CRECK [24]
15 (159 species and 268 reactions) and San Diego [25]
16 detailed mechanisms (57 species and 268 reactions).
17 The San Diego mechanisms has been successfully
18 tested for diluted flames [26]. The procedure to de-
19 fine ϕ_{bg} and ϕ_r in a 1D flame problem for the generic
20 fuel C_nH_m , is detailed in Supplementary material,
21 where the expressions of the functions $h_i(\phi_r, \phi_{bg})$ (7)
22 for the two-step mechanism are reported, along with
23 chemistry validation for other values of P and T .

24 4.3. Modeling stretch effects: S-TF model

25 The necessity to rework the Thickened Flame
26 model to correctly capture the effects of stretch on re-
27 solved thickened flame fronts has been recently iden-
28 tified by multiple authors [14-17]. The Stretched-
29 Thickened Flame model [15] (S-TF) is used here for
30 this purpose and extended to account for different
31 thermodynamic and dilution conditions. This exten-
32 sion is crucial for applications, like CVC, where the
33 fresh gas state, feeding a propagating flame, evolves
34 in time. For the sake of completeness, the principles
35 of the S-TF model are briefly recalled.

Fig. 4: $F = 1$ vs $F = 10$ (TF model) a) 1D strained flames (CFPF configuration) computed at different pressure b) 1D strained flames (CFPF configuration) computed at different dilution level.

36 Differently from the classical Thickened Flame
37 model, the S-TF proposes the application of differ-
38 ent factors for thermal diffusion (D_{th}), species dif-
39 fusion (D_k) and chemical source terms ($k_{f,i}$). This
40 operation can be summarized through the following
41 “mapping”:

$$\begin{cases} D_{th} \mapsto F_{th} D_{th} \\ D_k \mapsto F_{sp} D_k \\ k_{f,i} \mapsto F_r k_{f,i} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

42 F_{th} , F_{sp} and F_r are generalized thickening factors
43 which have to retrieve the classical TF model prop-
44 erties, (1) thicken the flame by a factor F , (2) pre-
45 serve the laminar flame speed s_L^0 , and extend them
46 for stretched flames. In Detomaso et al. [15], it is
47 demonstrated that constraints (1)-(2) are respected by
48 the following relations:

$$\begin{cases} F_{th} = F \\ F_{sp} = \frac{F^2 Le^0}{F + (Le^0 - 1) \tilde{X}_0} \\ F_r = \left[\frac{1}{F_{th}^{1/2}} \left(\frac{F_{th}}{F_{sp}} \right)^\alpha \right]^2 \end{cases}, \quad (9)$$

49 where Le^0 is the mixture Lewis number and α is a pa-
50 rameter depending on the chemical kinetics used. F
51 is the thickening factor of the classical TF model [7]
52 $F = n_p \Delta x / \delta_L^0$, where n_p is the number of points
53 needed in the flame front (usually 5 to 10), Δx the
54 local mesh size and δ_L^0 the unstretched laminar flame
55 thickness corresponding to local fresh gas conditions.
56 \tilde{X}_0 is a function of F and it is optimized to match the
57 consumption speed at arbitrary stretch target level k^t :

$$\tilde{X}_0 \quad \text{s.t.} \quad \hat{s}_c(F > 1, k^t) = s_c(F = 1, k^t), \quad (10)$$

58 where \hat{s}_c corresponds to the consumption speed of the
59 strained flame resolved by the S-TF model. The opti-
60 mization is performed relying on 1D Counter Flow
61 Premixed Flame configuration (CFPF) in CANTERA
62 (<https://cantera.org/>) at specified stretch k^t . k^t is typi-
63 cally set such that the associated Karlovitz number
64 is equal to unity: $Ka^t = k^t \delta_L^0 / s_L^0 = 1$. In this

1 1D flame configuration, strain k_s is computed by using
 2 the injection velocity of fresh (U_u) and burnt (U_b)
 3 products [14, 15]:

$$k_s = \frac{U_u + U_b}{L}, \quad (11)$$

4 where L is the distance between the two injection
 5 points. Note that the conclusions of this section are
 6 still valid independently of the accuracy in the defini-
 7 tion of strain.

8 The mapping of Eq. (8) is, in essence, an adjust-
 9 ment of the effective mixture Lewis number which,
 10 combined with Eq. (9), extends beyond the classi-
 11 cal TF model, ensuring an accurate reproduction of
 12 the flame response to stretch at least from $k = 0$ to
 13 $k = k^t$ [15]. Detomaso et al. [15] show that a simple
 14 parabolic dependence of \tilde{X}_0 in F is sufficient:

$$\tilde{X}_0 = \gamma(F - 1)^2 + 1, \quad (12)$$

15 where γ is the only parameter required to match the
 16 correct flame behavior for a large range of stretch and
 17 thickening values, and it may still depend on the mixture
 18 [15].

19 The capacity of the S-TF model to account for dif-
 20 ferent thermodynamic and dilution properties is as-
 21 sessed here. First, Fig. 4 recalls the limitation of the
 22 classical TF model: it does not predict the effect of
 23 stretch on s_c when the flame is thickened. By chang-
 24 ing fresh gas conditions (P and ϕ_{bg} at fixed $\phi_r =$
 25 0.9 and $T = 300\text{ K}$), thickened and non-thickened
 26 flames behave differently versus strain due to the im-
 27 pact of pressure (Fig. 4a) or dilution (Fig. 4b) on the
 28 flame burning velocity. This suggests that different
 29 functions \tilde{X}_0 are required to correct each operating
 30 point. However, Figs. 5 unveil that the impact of ϕ_{bg}
 31 and P on the behavior of the strain flames is self sim-
 32 ilar or close to self-similar in $Ka = k\delta_L^0/s_L^0$ for both
 33 $F = 1$ and $F = 10$ (with TF model). Since the rela-
 34 tions in Eqs. (9) embed s_L^0 and δ_L^0 in their derivation,
 35 as long as the flame response to stretch is mildly sen-
 36 sitive to operative conditions when stretch is scaled by
 37 δ_L^0/s_L^0 , the S-TF model predicts the correct flame be-
 38 havior without any additional adjustment accounting
 39 for the operating conditions. This is verified in Fig. 5
 40 where a single correcting function \tilde{X}_0 ($\gamma = -0.03$
 41 in Eq. (12) for $\phi_r = 0.9$, $T = 300\text{ K}$) is used for
 42 various ϕ_{bg} and P values with excellent agree-
 43 ment with reference solution ($F = 1$). Therefore, S-
 44 TF coefficients do not require further fitting and the
 45 model readjusts itself by taking into account varia-
 46 tions in unstrained flame parameters (laminar flame
 47 speed and flame thickness). This is not true for the
 48 influence of the effective equivalence ratio ϕ_r which
 49 impact has to be included in the correcting function
 50 \tilde{X}_0 , i.e. $\gamma \mapsto \gamma(\phi_r)$ [15].

51 4.4. Practical implementation in LES code

52 Fig. 5: TF vs S-TF model. a) 1D strained flames computed
 53 at different pressures. b) 1D strained flames computed
 54 at different dilution levels. Continuous and dashed lines corre-
 55 sponds to results obtained with the classical TF model while
 56 full symbols indicate the result of the S-TF model.

57 During the LES, the chemical mechanism and the
 58 turbulent combustion model require an accurate eval-
 59 uation of the local fresh gas conditions to correct ki-
 60 netics and estimate 1D flame properties. First, pres-
 61 sure of the flammable mixture is uniform in space and
 62 it is evaluated for each time-step, since it increases
 63 during the flame propagation in the CV2. Unburnt
 64 temperature is estimated assuming that fresh gases
 65 undergo an isentropic relation [10]. Before spark ig-
 66 nition, simulations show small local variations of the
 67 temperature field (around 10 K), justifying the adop-
 68 tion of a fresh gas temperature uniform in space and
 69 varying only with pressure. The intake phase homog-
 70 enizes the temperature field, bringing it to 300K
 71 Finally, as shown in Sect. 4.1, the mixture composition
 72 is completely defined by two parameters ϕ_{bg} and ϕ_r
 73 which must be therefore known locally by the LES.
 74 Equation 6 provides a relation between ϕ_r , ϕ_{bg} and
 75 ϕ_{tot} and the latter can be easily computed in the LES.
 76 Indeed, Bilger's mixture fraction [27] z_{tot} is classically
 77 used to compute locally the overall equivalence
 78 ratio ϕ_{tot} :

$$\phi_{tot} = \frac{s}{Y_{O_2}^0} \frac{z_{tot}}{1 - z_{tot}} \quad (13)$$

79 where $Y_{O_2}^0$ is the O_2 mass fraction in the pure air
 80 stream ($Y_{O_2}^0 = 0.233$), s is the mass stoichiometric
 81 ratio [1]. Thus, only one parameter (ϕ_{bg} or ϕ_r) has to
 82 be computed to deduce the other one through Eq. (6).

83 For a given cycle, ϕ_{bg} measures the oxidizer vitia-
 84 tion level (local amount of CO_2 and H_2O coming from
 85 previous cycles). Consequently, it is directly related

¹Mass fractions are used for practical reasons.

Fig. 6: Pressure signal measured in the chamber. Experimental signal vs LES results obtained with the S-TF model.

Fig. 7: a) Scatter plot of local mass fractions Y_{H_2O} vs Y_{CO_2} colored by ϕ_{bg} . b) Comparison between Eq. (6) and fuel-oxidizer molar ratio before spark ignition.

- 1 to the amount of fuel ($Y_{C_3H_8}^*$), burnt in the previous
2 combustion processes. In the LES, the mass fraction
3 $Y_{C_3H_8}^*$ is computed from the local values assumed by
4 z_{tot} [12] at the end of each cycle, here called \widehat{z}_{tot} :

$$Y_{C_3H_8}^* = \widehat{z}_{tot} - \widehat{Y}_{C_3H_8}. \quad (14)$$

- 5 where $\widehat{Y}_{C_3H_8}$ is the fuel mass fraction, unburnt in the
6 domain at end of the cycle. Once initialized cycli-
7 cally, $Y_{C_3H_8}^*$ is treated as a passive scalar, with its
8 own transport equation, which provides ϕ_{bg} (see Sup-
9 plementary material for analytical demonstration):

$$\phi_{bg} = \frac{s}{Y_{O_2}^0} \frac{Y_{C_3H_8}^*}{1 - z_{tot}}. \quad (15)$$

- 10 Finally, Eq. (6) is used to compute ϕ_r .

11 The procedure described in this section char-
12 acterizes the local fresh gas conditions and for
13 each iteration provides the desired local adjustment
14 of the chemical scheme ($h_i(\phi_r, \phi_{bg})$), the S-TF
15 model ($\gamma(\phi_r)$) and turbulent combustion modelling
16 ($s_L^0(\phi_r, \phi_{bg}, P, T)$, $\delta_L^0(\phi_r, \phi_{bg}, P, T)$).

17 5. Application to the CV2 chamber

18 In this section, the dilution model is applied to the
19 CV2 chamber to capture the local flow composition,
20 and the capacity of the S-TF model to mitigate the
21 amplification of flame response to stretch, typical of
22 the TF model, is assessed.

23 Figure 6 compares computed (LES with the S-TF
24 model) and measured (experiments) pressure signals
25 recorded inside the CV2 chamber. In the first cycle no
26 dilution is accounted for, a mixture of pure fuel and
27 air is ignited and a pressure peak of 17 bar is reached.
28 During the following cycles, RBG reduce the flame
29 speed and the adiabatic flame temperature, diminish-
30 ing the maximum pressure, which stabilizes around
31 14 bar.

32 Dilution is captured locally and Fig. 7 illustrates
33 how the dilution model (Sect. 4.1) is applied. The
34 instant right before spark ignition of the fourth cycle
35 ($t \approx 400$ ms) is considered. Mass fractions of CO_2
36 and H_2O (Fig. 7a) are linearly proportional, proving
37 that CO is completely re-associated before the
38 new combustion phase and the hypothesis of complete
39 combustion used in Sect. 4.1 is verified. For this reason,
40 ϕ_{bg} captures the mass fractions Y_{CO_2} and Y_{H_2O}
41 at the same time and provides the concentration of di-
42 lutants coming from the previous combustion phases.
43 Figure 7b compares the field of ϕ_r obtained with
44 Eq. (6) and with the ratio of reacting masses before
45 combustion. The analytical expression in Eq. (6) pro-
46 vides the expected ϕ_r field, preserving it also after
47 ignition. Across the flame front, chemical reactions
48 do not affect both the molar balance (ϕ_{tot}) and the
49 passive scalar $Y_{C_3H_8}^*$, which is transported with the
50 fuel diffusion properties. Consequently, ϕ_{bg} and ϕ_r

Fig. 8: Cycle 4. S-TF vs TF model. a) Pressure signal b) Averaged fuel consumption rate as a function of the mean stretch. $\max(dP/dt)$ indicated with the star-marker.

1 give the unburnt gas composition in every point of the
2 domain, at any moment.

3 The fourth cycle is now analysed to evaluate the
4 impact of the Stretched-Thickened Flame model on
5 the dynamics of this turbulent propagating flame. Figure
6 8a displays the pressure signal obtained with the
7 S-TF and the TF model. The pressure evolution pre-
8 dicted with the classical TF model falls outside the
9 experimental envelope. It underestimates the over-
10 pressure evolution during the combustion phase and
11 does not allow enough time for the isochoric cooling
12 phase to take place. The S-TF, on the other hand,
13 corrects these behaviors and provides an accurate depic-
14 tion of the pressure evolution during all phases of the
15 cycle. These differences can be supported by compar-
16 ing the averaged fuel consumption rate that the two
17 models give, which is representative of the averaged
18 consumption speed $\langle s_c \rangle$:

$$\langle s_c \rangle \propto \langle \dot{\omega}_F \rangle = \frac{1}{V} \int_V \dot{\omega}_F dV \quad (16)$$

19 where V is the entire chamber volume and $\dot{\omega}_F$ is the
20 local fuel consumption rate. Figure 8b evaluates the
21 averaged fuel consumption rate as a function of the
22 global stretch experienced by the flame [28]:

$$\langle k \rangle = \frac{1}{S_f} \frac{dS_f}{dt} \quad (17)$$

23 with S_f the area of an isosurface of 1500 K. Each
24 flame instant is colored with the averaged thickening
25 factor $\langle F \rangle$ (or $\langle F_{th} \rangle$) applied on the

Fig. 9: Ignition sequence. Experimental flame shape captured with the chemiluminescence technique compared with the heat release rate (HRR) signal computed with the LES simulation. White dashed line is used to highlight the flame.

26 flame. $\langle k \rangle$ represents the resolved stretch acting
27 on the flame front, which is accounted for by the S-
28 TF model [15]. Note that the effect of stretch at the
29 subgrid scale is not accounted for in the S-TF model.
30 The subgrid-scale turbulent combustion model [23]
31 accounts for only the lost contribution of turbulence
32 to flame wrinkling due to the thickening procedure.

33 Depending on the unstretched laminar flame thick-
34 ness δ_L^0 , $\langle F \rangle$ changes in time due to the evolu-
35 ting local composition and pressure conditions during
36 each cycle. As the flame kernel develops, $\langle k \rangle$ re-
37 duces, affecting the global flame speed. For the same
38 value of $\langle k \rangle$, the S-TF applies thickening values
39 similar to the TF model but corrects the amplification
40 of the flame sensitivity to stretch observed with TF,
41 and predicts considerably higher flame consumption
42 speeds. This effect enhances the pressure rise during
43 combustion (higher dP/dt) as expected. Note that the
44 point of maximum consumption speed coincides with
45 the maximum of dP/dt (star symbols in Fig. 8a and
46 b).

47 The impact of the S-TF model is also assessed in

Fig. 9] which compares the flame evolution obtained by the simulations, with the experimental signals measured with the chemiluminescence technique [2]. From LES, the heat release rate (HRR) is used to identify the flame and evaluate the two combustion models applied to the fourth cycle. The three instants are taken with respect to the ignition timing t_{ign} . Once ignited, the flame kernel freely propagates inside the chamber, stretched by the surrounding flow. Although both models provide the burning velocity of the unstretched turbulent flame segments, the S-TF improves the response of the stretched elements embedded in the flame brush, without requiring any information about the local stretch. The classical TF model yields a slow combustion phase caused by a weak flame with a propagation time higher than expected. Conversely, the Stretched-Thickened Flame model provides a better prediction of the flame dynamics during its propagation, improving the capacity to capture the unsteady chamber operation.

6. Conclusions

A consistent LES methodology for turbulent propagating flames in complex flow conditions is here proposed. The constant volume combustion chamber CV2, operating at the Pprime laboratory (Poitiers, France), is used as application test case since it contains numerous physical aspects common to multiple combustor systems and is a challenging case for modeling of ignition, high pressure combustion, dilution with RBG and stretch effects. A strategy to resolve diluted stretched flames at variable thermodynamic conditions is described. A dilution model developed for afterburners [11] has been adapted to the CV2 chamber. The Stretched-Thickened Flame model has been extended to different mixture conditions. The application of the numerical approach to the CV2 test case shows a remarkable improvement in the prediction of the flame dynamics. The capacity of the S-TF model to correct the TF model amplification of the flame response to stretch is proved in complex engines conditions.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary material

Supplementary material is submitted along with the manuscript.

References

- [1] L. Labarrere, T. Poinso, A. Dauplain, F. Duchaine, M. Bellenoue, B. Boust, Experimental and numerical study of cyclic variations in a Constant Volume Combustion chamber, *Combust. Flame* 172 (2016) 49–61.
- [2] Q. Michalski, B. Boust, M. Bellenoue, Influence of operating conditions and residual burned gas properties on cyclic operation of constant-volume combustion, in: *Notes Numer. Fluid Mech. Multidiscip. Des.*, Vol. 141, Springer International Publishing, 2019, pp. 215–233.
- [3] K. Kailasanath, *Recent developments in the research on pulse detonation engines*, Springer, 2002.
- [4] O. Vermorel, S. Richard, O. Colin, C. Angelberger, A. Benkenida, D. Veynante, Towards the understanding of cyclic variability in a spark ignited engine using multi-cycle LES, *Combust. Flame* 156 (8) (2009) 1525–1541.
- [5] V. Granet, O. Vermorel, C. Lacour, B. Enaux, V. Dugué, T. Poinso, Large-Eddy Simulation and experimental study of cycle-to-cycle variations of stable and unstable operating points in a spark ignition engine, *Combust. Flame* 159 (4) (2012) 1562–1575.
- [6] O. Colin, M. Rudgyard, Development of High-Order Taylor-Galerkin Schemes for LES, *J. Comput. Phys.* 162 (2) (2000) 338–371.
- [7] J. P. Legier, T. Poinso, D. Veynante, Dynamically thickened flame LES model for premixed and non-premixed turbulent combustion, *Proc. Summer Program, Cent. Turbul. Res.* (2000) 157–168.
- [8] G. Lacaze, E. Richardson, T. Poinso, Large eddy simulation of spark ignition in a turbulent methane jet, *Combust. Flame* 156 (10) (2009) 1993–2009.
- [9] S. J. Kazmouz, D. C. Haworth, P. Lillo, V. Sick, Large-eddy simulations of a stratified-charge direct-injection spark-ignition engine: Comparison with experiment and analysis of cycle-to-cycle variations, *Proc. Combust. Inst.* 38 (2021) 5665–5672.
- [10] N. Detomaso, D. Laera, P. Pouech, F. Duchaine, T. Poinso, Large Eddy Simulation of a Pistonless Constant Volume Combustor: A New Concept of Pressure Gain Combustion, *J. Eng. Gas Turbines Power* 145 (2) (2023) 1–10.
- [11] C. Mocquard, D. Laera, J. Dombard, T. Poinso, A two-step chemical scheme for auto-igniting and propagating kerosene flames at reheat conditions, *Combust. Flame* 248 (2023) 112558.
- [12] C. Mocquard, N. Detomaso, D. Laera, J. Dombard, P. Thierry, An extension of the thickened flame model for Large Eddy Simulations of auto-igniting flames in reheat systems, in: *11st Eur. Combust. Meet.*, Rouen, 2023.
- [13] P. S. Volpiani, T. Schmitt, D. Veynante, Large eddy simulation of a turbulent swirling premixed flame coupling the TFLES model with a dynamic wrinkling formulation, *Combust. Flame* 180 (2017) 124–135.
- [14] S. Popp, G. Kuenne, J. Janicka, C. Hasse, An extended artificial thickening approach for strained premixed flames, *Combust. Flame* 206 (2019) 252–265.
- [15] N. Detomaso, J. J. Hok, O. Dounia, D. Laera, T. Poinso, A generalization of the Thickened Flame

- 1 model for stretched flames, *Combust. Flame* 258
2 (2023) 113080.
- 3 [16] A. L. Comer, T. P. Gallagher, K. Duraisamy, B. A.
4 Rankin, A modified thickened flame model for sim-
5 ulating extinction, *Combust. Theory Model.* 26 (7)
6 (2022) 1262–1292.
- 7 [17] S. Poncet, C. Mehl, K. Truffin, O. Colin, Modified dif-
8 fusion model adapted to non-unity Lewis number mix-
9 tures for low flame stretch using the thickened flame
10 model, in: 11th Eur. Combust. Meet. 2023, Rouen,
11 2023, pp. 1–4.
- 12 [18] L. Bonneau, V. Robin, T. Xavier, A computational
13 framework combining a basic turbulent combustion
14 model, self-similar chemistry behavior, and a wall
15 thermal law adapted for large-eddy simulations of
16 a cyclically operating constant volume combustion
17 chamber, *Combust. Flame* 244 (2022) 112212.
- 18 [19] T. Schönfeld, M. Rudgyard, Steady and unsteady flow
19 simulations using the hybrid flow solver AVBP, *AIAA*
20 *J.* 37 (11) (1999) 1378–1385.
- 21 [20] O. Colin, A. Benkenida, C. Angelberger, 3D model-
22 ing of mixing, ignition and combustion phenomena in
23 highly stratified gasoline engines, *Oil Gas Sci. Technol.* 58 (1) (2003) 47–62.
- 24 [21] F. Nicoud, F. Ducros, Subgrid-scale stress modelling
25 based on the square of the velocity gradient tensor,
26 *Flow, Turbul. Combust.* 62 (3) (1999) 183–200.
- 27 [22] B. Franzelli, E. Riber, M. Sanjosé, T. Poinsot, A
28 two-step chemical scheme for kerosene-air premixed
29 flames, *Combust. Flame* 157 (7) (2010) 1364–1373.
- 30 [23] F. Charlette, C. Meneveau, D. Veynante, A power-law
31 flame wrinkling model for LES of premixed turbulent
32 combustion Part I: Non-dynamic formulation and ini-
33 tial tests, *Combust. Flame* 131 (1-2) (2002) 159–180.
- 34 [24] E. Ranzi, A. Frassoldati, A. Stagni, M. Pelucchi,
35 A. Cuoci, T. Faravelli, Reduced kinetic schemes of
36 complex reaction systems: Fossil and biomass-derived
37 transportation fuels, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.* 46 (9) (2014)
38 512–542.
- 39 [25] U. of California, Chemical-kinetic mechanisms for
40 combustion applications, san Diego Mechanism web
41 page, Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering.
- 42 [26] Y. N. Kochar, Laminar Flame Speed and Stretch Sensi-
43 tivity of Hydrocarbon Fuels at High Preheat and Pres-
44 sure, Ph.D. thesis, Georgia Institute of Technology
45 (2014).
- 46 [27] R. W. Bilger, S. H. Stårner, R. J. Kee, On re-
47 duced mechanisms for methaneair combustion in non-
48 premixed flames, *Combust. Flame* 80 (2) (1990) 135–
49 149.
- 50 [28] T. Poinsot, D. Veynante, Theoretical and numerical
51 combustion, Amazon, 2022.
- 52